

Minimal setup for setting up Convai LLMs with Metahumans in Unreal Engine 5

By Mikkel Nørtoft

Guest What can you tell me about the mle cathedral?

Cathedral Expert Ah, the Mikkeli Cathedral! It's a beautiful example of Gothic Revival architecture, built between 1896 and 1897 by Josef Stenbäck. The altarpiece is a masterpiece by Pekka Halonen. I can tell you much more if you'd like!

You can do this! Essential workflow using various presets.

(cf. also Convai's own quick setup tutorial at <https://youtu.be/HHJvY9dmwwg>)

Note: We will be switching between Unreal Engine (UE 5),
Metahuman Creator (in web browser), and
Convai (in web browser), so keep them open throughout

Install Epic Games Launcher, from there install Unreal Engine, go to metahuman.unrealengine.com (all free)

Sign in (with UE login) to **Metahuman Creator** (free)

Metahuman, Reallusion and ReadyPlayerME NPCs have most easy Convai integration, here we use a Metahuman

MetaHuman Version Selection

Version Unreal Engine 5.5

- Recommended for all creators.
- Latest version, up to date with all new features.
- Compatible with the latest version of UE, which may be newer than the selected version.

Launch MetaHuman Creator

MetaHuman Plugin for Unreal

- **MetaHuman Animator:** Facial performance capture for MetaHumans.
- **Mesh to MetaHuman:** Convert your custom mesh into a MetaHuman.

RECENT PROJECTS

GAMES

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ARCHITECTURE

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SIMULATION

Blank

First Person

Third Person

Top Down

Vehicle

Handheld AR

Virtual Reality

First Person

The first person template features a player character (represented by a pair of arms) which is viewed from first person perspective. The character can be moved around the level using keyboard, controller or virtual joystick on a touch device. Additionally the player can look around using mouse, controller or virtual joystick on a touch device. The character can also pick up a gun that, using mouse, controller or virtual joystick on a touch device will fire a simple sphere projectile

Project Defaults

BLUEPRINT **C++**

Target Platform **Desktop**

Quality Preset **Maximum**

Starter Content

Raytracing

Launch Unreal Engine,
 Choose a project template
 (1st or 3rd person, or VR, can
 be changed later),
 Give name and location,
 Create project

Project Location

Project Name

Create **Cancel**

Get Metahuman and Convai **plugins** from Fab.com, and enable them in the Epic Games Launcher's UE 5 library

For the scene, make a new project (1st/3rd person template) and add add the landscape "map" (from Fab.com)

A new amazing automaterial landscape level by UnrealityBytes is now freely available, see: https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=VA0PivT_vVw&ab_channel=UnrealityBites

Any other level you can find on Fab.com or elsewhere can also be used as the scene ("Map" in UE 5)

In UE 5, Go to Edit > Plugins (notice also Project settings for later)

Search for Convai and Metahuman and make sure they are enabled,
 May require restarting UE 5 after enabling

To get a Metahuman,
go to Window
(or the +Add button) > Quixel Bridge > Metahuman

FACE

- Blend
- Skin
- Eyes
- Teeth
- Makeup

HAIR

- Head
- Eyebrows
- Eyelashes
- Mustache
- Beard

BODY

- Proportions
- Tops
- Bottoms
- Shoes

BLEND ?

Studio Auto Medium LOD 0

PRESETS

In the Metahuman Creator, start by tweaking a preset character. Traits from three simultaneous other characters can be blended in at each separate point on the face, giving almost unlimited variability

HOTKEY REFERENCE

- Focus Point **RMB Click**
- Orbit **RMB Hold**
- Pan/Orbit **MMB**
- Pan **ALT + MMB**
- Zoom **ALT + RMB**
- Move Sculpt Point **LMB**
- Move Sculpt Point Forward **CTRL + LMB**
- Reset Sculpt Point **SHIFT + LMB**
- Rotate Lights **L + Mouse Move**
- Reset Lights **SHIFT + L**
- Toggle Clay Render **C**
- Face Camera **1**
- Body Camera **2**
- Torso Camera **3**
- Legs Camera **4**
- Feet Camera **5**
- Far Camera **6**
- Undo **CTRL + Z**
- Redo **CTRL + Y**

Idle Face ROM Body ROM Happy A Surprise

Body and clothes are somewhat more limited inside this platform, but other tools can help with this

Or strip to rig external clothes in free software (e.g. Blender), or (easier) paid software (MetaTailor, Marvellous Designer, etc.)

MetaTailor: very easy to import and rig external clothes to a metahuman skeleton, limited free plan, c. 3 costume exports, seemingly per month, so use wisely

Marvellous Designer
(detailed tailoring)

Custom clothes

If you made your own clothes and they don't have physics and chaos cloth properties yet (moving naturally with the character), this can also be generated in (currently) free programs Style3D or Jinny, and then rigged in Blender, MetaTailor or similar

Style3D:

<https://studio.style3d.com/en/home>

Jinny: <https://connect.clo-set.com/jinny>

https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=KFu3Z6re-Os&ab_channel=askNK guide to import external avatars with clothes and simulate their physics

Changing the name seems the easiest way to store the new character so it appears in UE 5's Quixel Bridge where we can download and add it to our UE 5 project

Load Landscape Pro 2.0 level (or any other UE level from the web)

Open Unreal Engine's Quixel Bridge

Make account on
Convai.com, create
character

Also, get API key here to
paste in UE 5 Project settings
> Plugins > Convai

Back in UE 5, go to
Project settings

Project Settings

[Widget Designer \(Team\)](#)

Platforms

[Android](#)[Android Material Quality - ES31](#)[Android Material Quality - Vulkan](#)[Android SDK](#)[Android SM5 Material Quality - Vulkan](#)[HoloLens](#)[iOS](#)[iOS Material Quality](#)[Linux](#)[Windows](#)

Plugins

[AndroidFileServer](#)[AVF Media](#)[▶ Convai](#)[Dataflow](#)[Fracture Mode](#)[Geometry Cache](#)[GooglePAD](#)[IMG Media](#)[Level Sequencer](#)[Modeling Mode](#)[Modeling Mode Tools](#)

Search

▼ Plugins - Convai

Configure Convai settings

 These settings are saved in DefaultEngine.ini, which is currently writable.

▼ Convai API

API Key

... and scroll down to Plugins > Convai,
and insert your Convai API key and close
the window

In Convai, add some backstory to the character.
You can change this at any time, and experiment

Character Description ↻ 🔄 Update ⋮

Character's Name Cathedral Expert **Character's ID** 1f045772-ff45-11ef-bb8f-42010a7be01a 📄

Core Description **Speaking Style** Embodiment 46/1000 words

Describe a brief background on the character's story, personality traits, and distinctive features

You're an expert on the history, architecture, construction, and social and religious importance of cathedrals. Your knowledge of cathedrals is unparalleled, earned through years of dedicated study and exploration. Your passion for unraveling their mysteries drives you to travel the world in search of new discoveries.

To not break the immersion, it may be a good idea to mention in the character's backstory the things that are in the scene or knowledge bank, you control the narrative 😊

🔄 Generate Core Description

Character Description

Avatar

Language And Speech

Knowledge Bank

Personality Traits

Core AI Settings **Choose LLM**

State Of Mind

Embodied Actions

Narrative Design **For extra narrative control**

Publish

Memory

Claude

Claude-3-5-Sonnet

Google

Gemini-Flash

Gemini-Pro

Llama

LLama3-70B

LLama2-13B

OpenAI

FT-GPT-3.5-Turbo

gpt-4o-mini

GPT-4o

Others

European

FT-Mistral-7B

Back in UE 5, go to Content Browser (bottom screen), find 1st/3rd person player blueprint, go to Class Settings, and in Parent Class (right screen) search "Convai" > ConvaiBasePlayer

Now in the Content browser find the Metahuman blueprint

Class Settings: Parent Class > ConvaiBaseCharacter

Components

- BP_Kim (Self)
- ConvaiChatbot
- ConvaiFaceSync
- Capsule
- Root
- Body
- Feet
- Face
- Mustache

My Blueprint

- convai
- Convai Chatbot
- Convai Face Sync
- Convai Player
- Convai Voice Comp

Left: Add both Convai Chatbot and Convai Face Sync components

Right: for Body: choose Anim Class Convai_MetaHuman_BodyAnim
For Face: choose Anim Class Convai_MetaHuman_FaceAnim

Details

Class Options

Parent Class

Convai Base Character

Advanced

Blueprint Options

- Run Construction Script on Drag
- Run Construction Script in Sequence
- Blueprint Display Name
- Blueprint Description
- Blueprint Namespace
- Blueprint Category

Reparent blueprint

- convai
- AI_Controller_Convai
- ConvaiBaseCharacter
- ConvaiBasePlayer
- ConvaiDemoGM
- ConvaiPlayerWithVoiceActivation

Animation

Animation Mode: Use Animation Blueprint

Anim Class

Disable Post Process Blueprint

Advanced

Mesh

Materials

Element 0

Convai_MetaHuman_Br

- convai
- None
- Convai_MetaHuman_BodyAnim
- Convai_MetaHuman_FaceAnim

Animation

Animation Mode: Use Animation Blueprint

Anim Class

Disable Post Process Blueprint

Advanced

Mesh

Materials

Element 0

Convai_MetaHuman_Fr

- convai
- None
- Convai_MetaHuman_BodyAnim
- Convai_MetaHuman_FaceAnim

Copy/Paste character ID from Convai character into Metahuman character in UE5

Character Description 🕒 🔄 Update ⋮

Character's Name Cathedral Expert

Character's ID 1f045772-ff45-11ef-bb8f-42 📄

Core Description **Speaking Style** Embodiment 750/1800 words

Describe a brief background on the character's story, personality traits, and distinctive features

Your name is Miika. You're an expert on the history, architecture, construction, and social and religious importance of cathedrals. Your knowledge of cathedrals is unparalleled, earned through years of dedicated study and exploration. Your passion for unraveling their mysteries drives you to travel the world in search of new discoveries.

You speak Finnish!

You especially know a lot about the Mikkeli Cathedral where you are the local tourist guide.

Details × **World Settings**

TestChar + Add ⌵

TestChar (Self)

ConvaiChatbot Edit in Blueprint

Search 📄 ★

General Actor LOD Misc Physics Rendering

Streaming **All**

Transform

Location	1380.0	1310.0	0.0
Rotation	0.0°	0.0°	0.0°
Scale	1.0	1.0	1.0

Default

Char ID 📄

Pawn Char ID

Drag the Metauman blueprint into the scene, hit PLAY and talk!
(holding **T** key)

And remember to turn on your PC mic!

(You may have to choose your PC mic input in UE project settings, and make sure your Windows sound mixer allows UE 5)

Guest Hello world.

Dolmen Gvay "Howdy there, partner! Just brushing off my dusty memory of the old world. What's this about a plague and a population collapse? Let me tell you something."

(here briefly testing another Convai "brain" by switching the character ID)

Hold [T] to Talk / Enter to Type

 convai

Tip: If you get “Texture Streaming Pool”-warning, follow this tutorial:

https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=uk3W8Zha hdg&ab_channel=UnrealEngine

Bonus: Sculpt the landscape (Landscape mode)

Paint the landscape!

Foliage mode, preloaded nature assets
in this “Landscape Pro 2.0” level
(can be switched)

With trees, rocks, buildings,
animals, people!, etc.

Adding trees in one
stroke

Download external 3D model

Many portals:

Sketchfab,
Turbosquid,
Fab.com (UE 5 main),
itch.io,
OpenGameArt

Loads of free models! (“assets”),
also levels, plugins, etc.

Import in Unreal Engine
(add to project or download and
drag into Content Browser, and
click “Import” (default settings))

Sketchfab

Q cathedral

Mikkeli Cathedral
3D Model

 Lassi Kaukonen
FOLLOWING

Nice name! :)

[Download 3D Model](#) + Add To </> Embed ↗ Share

Mikkeli Cathedral

Article Talk

Read Edit View history Tools

From Wikipedia, the free encyclopedia

Coordinates: 61°41′21.4″N 027°16′00.3″E﻿ / ﻿﻿ / ﻿

I learned something today!

This article has multiple issues. Please help **improve it** or discuss these issues [hide] on the **talk page**. *(Learn how and when to remove these messages)*

- This article **does not cite any sources**. *(October 2021)*
- You can help **expand this article with text translated from the [show] corresponding article in Finnish**. *(November 2015)* Click [show] for important translation instructions.

Mikkeli Cathedral is a large church in [Mikkeli](#), [Southern Savonia](#), [Finland](#), designed by Finnish church architect [Josef Stenbäck](#). It was built in 1896–1897 and represents the [Gothic Revival](#) style like many other churches designed by Stenbäck. The bell tower is in the western gable of the church. The church has 1,200 seats.

The organ was built in 1956 by [Kangasala](#) Organ Factory and has 51 stops. The altar painting "Crucified" was made by [Pekka Halonen](#) in 1899.

External links [edit]

- Media related to [Mikkeli Cathedral](#) at Wikimedia Commons
- [Bells \(.mp3\)](#)↗
- [Organ's disposition and other information](#)↗^[*permanent dead link*]

St. Michael's Cathedral

Mikkelin tuomiokirkko (in Finnish)
S:t Michels domkyrka (in Swedish)

St. Michael's Cathedral

Place cathedral in the scene (“Viewport”)
And position it as you want

Select, move, rotate, scale
“gizmos”

Get info about the Mikkeli Cathedral from the web (here using Perplexity.ai)

Tell me all there is to know about the Mikkeli Cathedral in Finland

Pro

38 sources

visitmikkeli
Mikkeli Cathedral

evendo
Mikkeli Cathedral: A Jewel of Finnish Architecture - ...

en.wikipedia
Mikkeli Cathedral - Wikipedia

+35 sources

Answer

Mikkeli Cathedral Overview

Mikkeli Cathedral, known locally as *Mikkelin Tuomiokirkko*, is a prominent Lutheran church located in Mikkeli, Southern Savonia, Finland. The cathedral is a landmark of Finnish architectural and cultural heritage, attracting visitors for its historical significance, Gothic Revival design, and vibrant community activities.

Historical Background

- Construction:** Built between 1896 and 1897 on Ristimäki Hill in the heart of Mikkeli 1 3 5 .
- Architect:** Designed by Josef Stenbäck, a renowned Finnish church architect known for his Gothic Revival style 1 3 4 .
- Altarpiece:** The altar painting, *Crucified*, was created by Finnish artist Pekka Halonen in 1899 1 3 4 .

Architectural Features

- Style:** Gothic Revival architecture with tall spires, intricate stained glass windows, and a bell tower located in the western gable 2 3 .

View More

Search Videos

Generate Image

Add info to character backstory in Convai, copy Character ID

The screenshot displays the Convai character editor interface. On the left is a vertical sidebar with navigation options: Character Description (highlighted in green), Avatar, Language And Speech, Knowledge Bank, Personality Traits, Core AI Settings, State Of Mind, Embodied Actions, Narrative Design, Publish, and Memory. The main content area is titled "Character Description" and includes an "Update" button. Below the title, there are two input fields: "Character's Name" containing "Cathedral Expert" and "Character's ID" containing "1f045772-ff45-11ef-bb8f-42010a7be01a". The "Character's ID" field is circled in red. Below these fields are three tabs: "Core Description" (selected), "Speaking Style", and "Embodiment". A word count "348/1000 words" is visible. The "Core Description" section contains a text area with the following content:

Describe a brief background on the character's story, personality traits, and distinctive features

You're an expert on the history, architecture, construction, and social and religious importance of cathedrals. Your knowledge of cathedrals is unparalleled, earned through years of dedicated study and exploration. Your passion for unraveling their mysteries drives you to travel the world in search of new discoveries.

You especially know a lot about the Mikkeli Cathedral where you are the local tourist guide.

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Historical Background
Construction: Built between 1896 and 1897 on Ristimäki Hill in the heart of Mikkeli.

Architect: Designed by Josef Stenbäck, a renowned Finnish church architect known for his Gothic Revival style.

Additional 1MB knowledge bank (c. 290 text pages), Convai uses RAG to extract info from these in real-time during conversation

- Character Description
- Avatar
- Language And Speech
- Knowledge Bank
- Personality Traits
- Core AI Settings
- State Of Mind
- Embodied Actions

Knowledge Bank

[Learn more on how to use Knowledge Bank](#)

My Documents

Upload Knowledge

Add Knowledge

Available files on your account

NAME	SIZE	STATUS	
DolmenGuy_extended_ba...	759 Bytes	File available	Connect
Otherworld.txt	2.06 KB	File available	Connect
Seersholm_etal2024_plag...	3.86 KB	File available	Connect
Dolmen_Guy_bank.txt	4.27 KB	File available	Connect
Dolmen_Debbie_bank.txt	2.01 KB	File available	Connect

Connect character to knowledge bank(s).

Tip: if loading forever, go to Playground and back to character and try again

Choose preferred AI language model

GPT-4o-mini:

Very light, minimal energy use in conversations

FT-Mistral-7B:

French company, also light enough to run on a PC (with decent GPU), but Convai runs in cloud

Character Description

Avatar

Language And Speech

Knowledge Bank

Personality Traits

Core AI Settings

State Of Mind

Embodied Actions

Narrative Design

Core AI Settings

Enable Moderation Filter

On **Convai's extra moderation filter**

These filters prevent potential violations, such as hate speech, profanity, and explicit content, in the chat.

Note: Disabling Moderation Filter will render functionalities like Narratives and Actions unavailable.

Select Foundation Model

Choose from a diverse range of LLM models.

Note: Some Models are not available when Moderation Filter is turned on.

gpt-4o-mini

OpenAI

gpt-4o-mini

GPT-4o

Others

FT-Mistral-7B

Talk to the Metahuman and learn!

Guest What can you tell me about the mle cathedral?
Cathedral Expert Ah, the Mikkeli Cathedral! It's a beautiful example of Gothic Revival architecture, built between 1896 and 1897 by Josef Stenbäck. The altarpiece is a masterpiece by Pekka Halonen. I can tell you much more if you'd like!

Expanded workflow (example): **extra functions, customisation, own photogrammetry**

Many(!) free 3D assets available

Let's check some free ones I found, +new free assets can be claimed every 14 days on Fab.com
Or make your own 3D assets with Reality Capture, free in Epic Games Launcher, or sculpt in Blender, generate them from image(s) in [Trellis](#), [Hunyan3D](#), etc. on HuggingFace platform

"Metahuman clothes" search on Fab.com

Meta Clothes Designer

Metahuman - Medieval Clothes & Dress II (Metahuman Clothing)

3D Models > Clothing & Jewelry > Clothing

Military I

Clothing
Mukilartz
Free

Poncho

Taqiya Yellow (W) (Kazakh Traditional Headr...

Balaclava - scarf as a hood - 3

Frock Coat

Bar patrons outfits

Georgian O

Bearded man in a traditional scotti

Elizabethan Outfit
a9908244
Free

Summer sports clothing
TijerinArt
Free

Victorian Childs outfit

Victorian Dress

CROPCRAFT
STUDIOS

How would you disseminate your research in a 3D world with AI characters?

when it came to construction. They used sledges and wooden frames to move those hefty stones, sometimes traveling a kilometer or so. They'd dig sockets for the upright stones and pack 'em in tight with smaller stones and clay. It took a whole lotta sweat and teamwork to raise those massive capstones, but they did it with sheer determination. Oh the trowels and tribulations they must've faced! Ain't that somethin'?